

Synthesis of [1,3,4]thiadiazino[2,3-*b*]quinazoline-3,6-diones

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2*H*, 6*H*-[1,3,4] thiadiazino [2,3-*b*] quinazoline-3,6(4*H*)-dione(Va) and 4-phenyl-2*H*, 6*H*-[1,3,4] thiadiazino [2,3-*b*] quinazoline-3,6(4*H*)-dione(Vb) have been synthesised by the condensation of chloroacetic acid(II) with 3-amino-2-mercaptoquinazoline-4(3*H*)-one(Ia) and 3-anilino-2-mercaptoquinazoline-4(3*H*)-one(Ib) respectively, followed by cyclisation with acetic anhydride in the presence of pyridine.

THE fusion of quinazoline ring with other biologically active nuclei has aroused considerable interest for synthetic organic chemists because many members of this family exhibit important biological activity. Recently Lempert *et al*¹ reported the synthesis of some [1,3,4] thiadiazino [3,2-*c*] quinazolines. Here we wish to report the synthesis of a few [1,3,4] thiadiazino [2,3-*b*] quinazoline-3,6(4*H*)-diones(V). These have been synthesised by the condensation of 3-amino/anilino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3*H*)-one(I) with chloroacetic acid(II) in the presence of sodium hydroxide or by refluxing in ethanol. The intermediates [(3-amino/anilino-3,4-dihydro-4-oxo-2-quinazoliny)thio] acetic acids(III) have been characterised on the basis of analysis, IR and PMR. IR of IIIa showed bands at 1695 and 1665 cm⁻¹ due to C=O of the -COOH and

respectively. It also showed a band at 2700-2550 cm⁻¹ due to -OH of the -COOH. Besides two bands originally present in 3-amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3*H*)-one at 3250 and 3180 cm⁻¹ remained intact. In its PMR† (IIIa, R=H) (in CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) showed a multiplet (4H) at 7.20-8.14 assignable to four aromatic protons. It also exhibited a singlet (2H) at 6.33 due to methylene protons adjacent to -COOH group

appeared as a broad signal at 3.15.

Similarly compound IIIb, in its IR showed bands at 1700 cm⁻¹ with shoulder at 1665 cm⁻¹

due to C=O of COOH and respectively. N-H stretching band appeared at 3230 cm⁻¹ and

-OH of -COOH appeared as broad band at 2700-2525 cm⁻¹.

IIIa on cyclisation with acetic anhydride in the presence of pyridine yielded the desired product i.e., 2*H*, 6*H*-[1,3,4] thiadiazino [2,3-*b*] quinazoline-3,6(4*H*)-dione (Va). Structure Va finds support from its analysis, IR and PMR spectral data. In its IR, the band at 3250 cm⁻¹ remained intact. Besides two new bands appeared at 1710 and 1670 cm⁻¹ instead of bands at 1695 and 1665 cm⁻¹ originally present in IIIa. PMR of Va (in CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) showed a multiplet (4H) at 7.25-8.14 assignable to aromatic protons. Besides, it showed a singlet (2H) at 2.43 assignable to methylene proton adjacent to

In a similar fashion, [(3-anilino-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxo-2-quinazoliny) thio] acetic acid(IIIb) was also cyclised to 4-phenyl-2*H*, 6*H*-[1,3,4] thiadiazino [2,3-*b*] quinazoline-3, 6(4*H*)-dione (Vb). In its IR band at 1700 cm⁻¹ originally present in IIIb became somewhat broader and appeared at 1700-1680 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in paraffin liquid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra, in nujol, were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 and PMR spectra on Varian EM-390 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal reference.

*Condensation of 3-amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3*H*)-one with chloroacetic acid i.e., Isolation of [(3-amino-3,4-dihydro-4-oxo-2-quinazoliny)thio] acetic acid (IIIa) :*

Method A : To the solution of 3-amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4(3*H*)-one (Ia) (1.93 g, 0.01 mole) in absolute ethanol (400 ml) were added anhydrous

† Chemical shifts are in δ(ppm).

sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mole) and chloroacetic acid (II) (0.94 g, 0.01 mole). The contents were refluxed over steam bath for 15 hrs. After removing ethanol under reduced pressure, the residue was poured over crushed ice (100 g). A solid thus separated was collected under suction and washed with ice cold water. Crystallisation from ethanol gave white shining plates, m.p. 247°; yield 2.0 g (80%). Found: C, 48.10; H, 3.62; N, 16.00. $C_{10}H_9N_3O_3S$ requires C, 47.81; H, 3.59; N, 16.73%. IR: ν_{max} 3250, 3180, 2700-2550, 1695, 1665, 1620, 1520, 1260, 1225, 1175, 1160, 1070, 1000, 910, 860, 770 and 750 cm^{-1} .

Method B: To the solution of 3-amino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4 (3*H*)-one (Ia) (1.93 g, 0.01 mole) in 5% sodium hydroxide (8 ml, 0.4 g, 0.01 mole) was added chloroacetic acid (II) (0.94 g, 0.01 mole) dissolved in water (4 ml) with continuous stirring at room temperature. The contents were kept overnight. On dilution with water, a solid thus separated was collected under suction, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol. It was found to be identical with the sample obtained by method A by its m.p., mixed m.p., TLC and superimposable IR spectrum.

Similarly condensation of 3-anilino-2-mercaptoquinazolin-4 (3*H*)-one (Ib) with chloroacetic acid resulted in the formation of [(3-anilino-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxo-2-quinazolinyl) thio] acetic acid (IIIb) with m.p. 228° (ethanol) in 50% yield. Found: C, 58.62; H, 4.09; N, 12.90. $C_{16}H_{13}N_3O_3S$ requires C, 58.72; H, 3.98; N, 12.84%. IR: ν_{max} 3230, 2700-2525, 1700, 1665, 1620, 1600, 1300, 1260, 1220, 1170, 920, 850 and 750 cm^{-1} .

Cyclisation of [(3-amino-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxo-quinazolinyl) thio] acetic acid with acetic anhydride and pyridine i.e., Synthesis of 2*H*, 6*H*-[1,3,4] thiadiazino [2,3-*b*] quinazoline-3,6(4*H*)-dione (Va):

To the mixture of acetic anhydride (0.75 ml) and pyridine (2.5 ml) was added [(3-amino-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxo-quinazolinyl) thio] acetic acid (IIIa) (700 mg). The contents were heated on a steam bath for two hrs. A clear solution thus obtained, was cooled to room temperature and poured over crushed ice (120 g). A sticky solid was obtained

which changed into crystalline mass by washing it with several portions of ice cold water. It was collected under suction and crystallised from ethanol into cream coloured needles, m.p. 212°; yield 500 mg (77%). Found C, 51.62; H, 3.12; N, 17.82. $C_{16}H_{11}N_3O_3S$ requires C, 51.50; H, 3.00; N, 18.03%. IR: ν_{max} 3240, 1710, 1670, 1610, 1240, 1200, 1000, 940, 790 and 750 cm^{-1} .

Similarly cyclisation of [(3-anilino-3, 4-dihydro-4-oxo-quinazolinyl) thio] acetic acid (IIIb) yielded 4-phenyl-2*H*, 6*H*-[1,3,4] thiadiazino [2,3-*b*] quinazoline-3, 6(4*H*)-dione (Vb), m.p. 202-4°; yield being 75%. Found: C, 61.98; H, 3.70; N, 13.42. $C_{16}H_{11}N_3O_3S$ requires C, 62.14; H, 3.56; N, 13.59%. IR: ν_{max} 1700-1680(b), 1620, 1600, 1300, 1250, 1190, 920 and 750 cm^{-1} .

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